

Potentiometric Studies of Some Poly-hydroxy Phenolic Mixed Ligand Chelates with Praseodymium (III)

T. H. MHASKE and K. N. MUNSHI

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University Campus, Nagpur

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Mixed ligand complex formation constants (K_{MAL}), where $M = Pr^{3+}$; $A = N$ -Hydroxyethyl-ethylene-diaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA) or Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) and $L =$ pyrogallol (PGL), pyrocatechol (PYC), protocatechuic acid (PCA) or protocatechualdehyde (PCAD) have been determined by using modified form of Irving-Rossotti technique at three different temperatures and in 0.2M ($NaClO_4$) ionic strength. Studies in case of PCAD were done in 50% v/v aqueous-dioxan media. Values of $\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$ have been found to be greater than the $\log K_{MAL}^{HEDTA}$ with Pr(III). Evidence for a co-ordination number larger than six in the rare-earths is presumed.

IN the present paper an attempt has been made to study the K_{MAL} of Pr(III) systems, where $A =$ HEDTA or NTA as primary ligands and $L =$ polyhydroxy phenolic compounds like pyrogallol (PGL), pyrocatechol (PYC), protocatechuic acid (PCA) or protocatechualdehyde (PCAD) as secondary ligands. [Pr(III) - (HEDTA)] chelate which is known to occupy five co-ordinating positions of Pr(III) have been reported¹ to have the value of $\log K = 14.61$. The value of $\log K$ for [Pr(III)-(NTA)] is reported² as 10.47. These complexes of HEDTA and NTA with Pr(III) are quite stable and hence found suitable to be used as primary ligands. Secondary ligands were chosen on the basis that the stability of secondary ligand complex with metal should be quite less than primary complex. So, there should not be replacement reaction such as

The values of $\log K_{MAL}$ obtained for the above systems at three different temperatures by using the modified form of Irving-Rossotti technique³ are reported in this paper for the first time. Due to less solubility of PCAD in water, all experiments with it were done in 50% v/v water-dioxan media.

Experimental

Materials: A stock solution of 0.02M of $PrCl_3 \cdot 7H_2O$ (Indian Rare-Earths Ltd.) was prepared in calculated quantity of perchloric acid and its metal content was estimated by spectrophotometric method⁴. A stock solution of 0.01M NTA (BDH), 0.01M HEDTA (Sigma Chemical Co.), 0.02M PGL (baker, Analysed), 0.02M PYC (Riedel) & 0.01M PCA (Fluka AG) were prepared in doubly distilled water. A stock solution of 0.01M PCAD (Fluka AG) was prepared in purified dioxan. All these solutions were standardised potentiometrically. All these solutions of secondary ligands were freshly prepared before use and care was taken to avoid their oxidation. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.0M) was prepared by a standard technique⁵, using AnalaR sample of E. Merck and was standardised potentiometrically against potassium hydrogen phthalate. The stock

solution of sodium perchlorate (Neutral) and perchloric acid (0.1M) was prepared by dissolving Anala R sample of $NaClO_4 \cdot H_2O$ (Riedel) and $HClO_4$ (E. Merck).

Apparatus: An expanded scale pH-meter, with accuracy ± 0.02 pH units, supplied by the Electronic Corporation of India with a glass calomel electrode assembly was used. The saturated calomel electrode was connected to the cell externally by means of an agar agar bridge, saturated with KNO_3 to prevent the formation of chloro-complexes. The design of the cell was such that it allowed flushing of nitrogen through the solution and also enabled measurements to be carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The temperature was maintained by immersing the cell in an Ultrathermostat bath (U-10, East Germany) having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Procedure: For the study of mixed ligand complexes the following systems were prepared.

- $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid.
- $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand.
- $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Pr^{3+} solution.
- $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Pr^{3+} solution + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand.

In each case total volume was made up to 100ml. and ionic strength was initially raised to 0.2M by adding the appropriate amount of neutral $NaClO_4$ solution. In case of PCAD 50% v/v aqueous - dioxan media was maintained. In each case the ratio between M:A:L was kept as 1:1:1. The four titration curves are referred as (A) Acid titration curve, (B) Secondary ligand titration curve, (C) Primary complex titration curve and (D)

Mixed ligand titration curve, Titrations with 1.06M NaOH were carried out at three different temperatures.

Fig. 1. Titration curves for [Pr(III)(NTA)(PGL)] complex at 25°, at $\mu=0.2M$.
 Curve (A) Acid titration curve.
 (B) Secondary ligand titration curve.
 (C) Primary complex titration curve.
 (D) Mixed ligand complex titration curve.

A typical plot of pH against volume of alkali have been represented in Fig. 1 for [Pr(III)(NTA)(PGL)] system and in Fig. 2 for [Pr(III)(HEDTA)(PGL)] system. The nature of the curves are similar in other systems.

Results and Discussion

Proton - ligand stability constants for the secondary ligands are calculated by using Irving - Rossotti technique and the values have already been reported in our earlier paper⁶. The same values are used for the calculation of K_{MAL} values.

An observation of mixed ligand system curves (Fig. 1-2), shows that in case of primary complex curve there is a lowering of pH indicating that primary complex formation takes place at very low pH. The calculation of \bar{n} shows that 1:1 complex formation is complete up to pH ~ 4.0. [Pr(III)(HEDTA)(OH)_n] could not form up to pH ~ 10.0 which indicates that the primary complex

Fig. 2. Titration curves for [Pr(III)(HEDTA)(PGL)] complex at 25°, at $\mu=0.2M$.
 Curve (A) Acid titration curve.
 (B) Secondary ligand titration curve.
 (C) Primary complex titration curve.
 (D) Mixed ligand complex titration curve.

formed at low pH is quite stable. [Pr(III)(NTA)] curve however diverges from NTA curve showing the formation of [Pr(III)(NTA)(OH)_n] after pH ~ 6.5 which again decomposes after pH ~ 8.5 forming metal hydroxide. Primary complex curve (C) and mixed complex curve (D) overlap each other at low pH. This indicates that in the pH range where primary ligand combines with metal, combination of polyhydroxy phenolic ligand does not take place. Since the dissociation of PGL, PYC and PCAD is negligible at low pH the curve (C) and curve (D) overlap. In case of these ligands, curve (D) diverges from curve (C) after pH 4.0. In this range, combination of secondary ligand with primary complex starts. The reaction can be represented as follows, omitting charges.

In case of PCA the curve (D) separates from curve (C) at lower pH due to the self dissociation of carboxylic group. Since the dissociation of primary complex does not take place in the range of dissociation of secondary ligand, it can be considered that the secondary ligand combines with primary complex just as it does with [M(aq)_n]³⁺ in binary systems. In presence of secondary

ligands. formation of $[\text{Pr(III)}(\text{A})(\text{OH})_n]$ is suppressed. The horizontal distance between curve (A) and curve (B) can be measured and subtracted from the horizontal distance between curve (C) and curve (D) and used for calculation of \bar{n} , where \bar{n} is average number of phenolic ligands associated with the primary complex. The equation for the calculation of \bar{n} is the same as in the original paper³, where T°_{OM} is the concentration of primary complex which is the concentration of Pr(III) . Again a typical plot for \bar{n} against pL for

Fig. 3. Formation curves of $[\text{Pr(III)}(\text{A})(\text{PGL})]$ complex at three different temperatures and at $\mu=0.2M$.

Fig. 4. Formation curves of $[\text{Pr(III)}(\text{HEDTA})(\text{PGL})]$ complex at three different temperatures and at $\mu=0.2M$.

$[\text{Pr(A)}(\text{PGL})]$ systems are shown in Fig. 3 and 4. The values of $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{NTA}}$ and $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{HEDTA}}$ have been given in Table 1.

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES AT $\mu=0.2$

System	Constant	Temperature		
		25°	35°	45°
$\text{Pr(III)}(\text{NTA})(\text{PGL})$	$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{NTA}}$	4.28	4.45	4.52
$\text{Pr(III)}(\text{NTA})(\text{PYC})$	$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{NTA}}$	5.08	4.98	4.87
$\text{Pr(III)}(\text{NTA})(\text{PCA})$	$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{NTA}}$	3.52	3.47	3.41
* $\text{Pr(III)}(\text{NTA})(\text{PCAD})$	$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{NTA}}$	5.43	5.34	5.28
$\text{Pr(III)}(\text{HEDTA})(\text{PGL})$	$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{HEDTA}}$	4.26	4.35	4.48
$\text{Pr(III)}(\text{HEDTA})(\text{PYC})$	$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{HEDTA}}$	4.62	4.48	4.22
$\text{Pr(III)}(\text{HEDTA})(\text{PCA})$	$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{HEDTA}}$	3.39	3.28	3.16
* $\text{Pr(III)}(\text{HEDTA})(\text{PCAD})$	$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{HEDTA}}$	5.26	5.13	5.02

*Experiments in 50% dioxan.

The order of the stability constants of mixed ligand complexes with change in secondary ligands is $\text{PCAD} > \text{PYC} > \text{PGL} > \text{PCA}$; this is in order of the basicity of ligands. PCAD however shows more stability than PYC because this system has been done in dioxan media as reported earlier. The stability however also changes if we keep the same secondary ligands but vary primary ligand. It is seen that $[\text{Pr(III)}(\text{NTA})(\text{L})]$ complexes are more stable than corresponding $[\text{Pr(III)}(\text{HEDTA})(\text{L})]$ complexes. All these secondary ligands are bidentate and co-ordination takes place through two ortho-hydroxy groups. $[\text{Pr(NTA)}]$ chelate has a lower electrostatic repulsion for incoming secondary ligands because of its neutral nature and NTA occupies only four co-ordination positions. However $[\text{Pr(HEDTA)}]$ chelate is also neutral but HEDTA occupies five co-ordination positions and hence the Pr(III) has to expand its co-ordination number greater than six to form the mixed ligand complexes of $[\text{Pr(III)}(\text{HEDTA})]$ with secondary ligands and this results in $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{NTA}}$ values higher than $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{HEDTA}}$. As reported in our earlier paper⁶ $[\text{Pr(EDTA)}]$ forms similar mixed ligand complexes with the above secondary ligands. The $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{EDTA}}$ values have been found to be even lower than $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{HEDTA}}$. This

can be accounted because of the expansion of co-ordination number of Pr(III) from six to eight and also because of the fact that the primary complex is a negatively charged species, $[\text{Pr(EDTA)}]^-$ and thus will exert an electrostatic force of repulsion on approaching negatively charged secondary ligands. Thus the concept of expansion of co-ordination number of lanthanides⁷⁻⁹ to seven or eight is also confirmed by the present study.

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